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***ISAMAPA: IDENTIFYING IDEAL TEMPLATES FOR GIS-BASED FLOOD
HAZARD MAPS IN DISASTER-PRONE COMMUNITIES WITHIN DAVAO CITY***

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This paper prepared by FAYE JANICA V. CABIZA with the title: "**ISAMAPA: IDENTIFYING IDEAL TEMPLATES FOR GIS-BASED FLOOD HAZARD MAPS IN DISASTER-PRONE COMMUNITIES WITHIN DAVAO CITY**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

Faye Janica Cabiza is a dedicated communications practitioner with over six years of experience in the development sector. Currently, she is doing freelance work in the fields of social media management, digital marketing, and public relations for various organizations.

Born in Davao City, Philippines, she earned her undergraduate degree in Communication Arts from the University of the Philippines Mindanao. She immediately worked for a local nonprofit organization based in the city where she first got inspired by the efforts of the Purok Disaster Action Team.

She also served as a national volunteer for Voluntary Service Overseas in partnership with the United States Agency for International Development where she spearheaded efforts to promote education and literacy in Paquibato District, Davao City. Later on, she went back to UP Mindanao and became the Information Officer for a grassroots initiative on artificial intelligence research and development project.

Looking ahead, she wants to devote her passion to the communications field to help the local development sector. She believes that community-based efforts serve as the foundation of societal progress fostering collaboration and empowerment among individuals.

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Dedication

In humble recognition and heartfelt appreciation of the unsung heroes—the Purok Disaster Action Team responders.

This thesis is dedicated to the resilient individuals who, in the face of adversity, demonstrated unwavering strength. Your selfless contributions to disaster response have been the guiding light in understanding the dynamics of disaster management. Your commitment to helping others during times of crisis are a testament to the human spirit.

It is through your shared experiences, knowledge, and tireless efforts that this thesis has been enriched. In times of disaster, you did not only help rebuild what was lost but also inspire a sense of hope within your community. This work stands as a tribute to your remarkable ambition and the invaluable lessons you have imparted through your duty in serving the people.

No disaster, regardless of its magnitude, can eclipse the unquenchable hope that you embody. You are a testament to the indomitable strength that emerges from the very core of humanity when faced with the most challenging circumstances.

Padayon!

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Abstract

Isamapa: Identifying ideal templates for GIS-based flood hazard maps in disaster-prone communities within Davao City

This study investigates the creation of optimal templates for Geographic Information System (GIS)-based flood hazard maps in disaster-prone communities within Davao City. The areas that were included in the study are identified by the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office as two of the flood-prone barangays in the city. Utilizing comprehensive spatial data and advanced GIS techniques, the research aims to identify and assess the most effective template designs for accurately representing flood hazards with the help of the Purok Disaster Action Team (PDAT).

Data was collected by conducting key informant interviews with several PDAT respondents in the identified flood-prone areas. The research revealed the templates that provide user-friendly visualization of flood-prone zones enabling better disaster preparedness and response strategies. Guided by the theory of Visual Rhetoric by Sonja K. Foss, the study highlights the importance of maps as a vital communication tool for decision-makers to facilitate proactive community-based measures. In turn, the research advocates to mitigate the impact of floods ultimately enhancing the resilience of the communities in Davao City.

Keywords: Geographic information system, flood hazard maps, disaster response, community mapping

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

The concept of Geographic Information System (GIS) was first introduced in the 1960s by Roger Tomlinson to determine the land usage in Canada. In the 1990s, the concept evolved into a technology named ArcView developed by Esri Software which used to be available for desktop computers only. One of the first users of GIS was the United States Military wherein the technology was used in a variety of applications including intelligence, battlefield management, and monitoring of possible terrorist activity (GIS Learning, 2002). Now, GIS is incorporated into every smartphone device and computer in the market. As a matter of fact, even the geo-tagged locations on Facebook and Instagram are also considered applications of GIS.

GIS is widely used in different fields including but not limited to land use planning, disaster management, agricultural applications, taxation, and natural resources management. In the Philippines, most public agencies utilize GIS to address land concerns such as property surveys and soil erosion. However, the growing number of disasters that hit the Philippines continues to increase in intensity over the years. In 2020, two typhoons named Ulysses and Rolly hit the country in less than a month. Both storms were likened to typhoons Ondoy and Yolanda respectively that brought heavy casualties in lives and properties. Up until now, the

possibilities of harnessing the potential of GIS to address disaster-related concerns have not been maximized.

Project Nationwide Operational Assessment of Hazards (NOAH) was launched in 2012 by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) to address the lack of tools and information to mitigate natural calamities. Project NOAH uses remote sensing through GIS technology to map out the country's flood-prone areas, major river systems, and watersheds. Aside from the maps, NOAH also managed to put up the Flood Information Network (FloodNET) Project that will provide timely and accurate information for flood early warning systems (Official Gazette of the Philippines, n.d.). However, the project was terminated in 2017 by DOST due to the lack of funding from the government. NOAH launched mobile applications that gave civilians ample time to prepare for possible floods near their area.

All disasters are spatial in nature hence, GIS techniques act as a decision-support tool. The evolution of computer technology and the availability of hardware are helpful for the rapid expansion of GIS in both disaster research and practice (Pore, 2013). There are maps that are produced by various government agencies yet the interpretations rarely reach the community. Despite the growing popularity of the technology, the use of GIS in disaster management is still not localized up to the grassroots level. In Davao City, the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO) is equipped with GIS-based flood hazard maps of 182 barangays in the city covering the entire stretch of the Davao River and its tributaries. However, local communities rarely get the chance to be informed on which areas of their barangays are considered flood-prone. As a result, they rely on CDRRMO in times of disasters instead of taking the initiative to organize community-based action groups

which was clearly stated under Republic Act 10121 or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010.

Under the said act, local communities actively engage in the identification, analysis, treatment, monitoring, and evaluation of disaster risks in order to enhance their capacities (National Disaster Coordinating Council, n.d.). The law encourages the creation of community-based disaster risk reduction and management organizations at the local level to empower people to participate in keeping their communities safe. As a matter of fact, other communities take it upon themselves to establish a purok system wherein residents at the purok level are trained to respond to different disasters by the city government and *barangay*.

Mapping is considered a vital tool in disaster response since data enables local authorities to determine the number of people who need assistance on the ground. While the entire population relies on Google Maps, there are communities in developing countries that do not exist on any digital map. As a result, local communities find it difficult to address their development problems with accurate spatial reference. Hence, the importance of visual communication in flood hazard maps is essential so local communities can easily identify vulnerable households that might be affected in times of disaster.

Statement of the Problem

Barton and Barton (1993) suggest that visual representations such as maps are “seen as complicit with social-control mechanisms inextricably linked to power and authority.” Based on this description, maps are considered an object of visual communication in a way where it serves as a medium between the mapmaker and

the audience. However, GIS-based flood hazard maps often fail to reach vulnerable communities that can greatly benefit from such information. In addition, map layouts tend to be universal instead of localizing the template to fit the level of understanding of the audience. With this, the researcher answered the following questions:

1. What are the insights and lived experiences of the purok members in relation to the GIS-based flood hazard map templates?
2. What are the best guidelines for writing and designing GIS information with the general and low-literate public?
3. How do the general and low literate public interpret the flood hazard maps of their respective communities?

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to determine the impact of visual communication in GIS-based flood hazard maps of select urban areas in Davao City. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Identify the insights of the purok members from chosen communities regarding the most effective layout of GIS-based flood hazard maps that are easily understandable, especially in times of disasters
2. Determine the best way of illustrating GIS-based maps to cater to the level of understanding of the general public especially local communities in flood-prone areas
3. Understand how local communities interpret the traditional layout of a GIS-based flood hazard map and identify ways to improve said template

Significance of the Study

Flood hazard maps are often interpreted as a mere two-dimensional representation of a certain community. However, mapping plays a vital role when it comes to disaster response since a map holds such a huge amount of data that can greatly help communities prevent further casualties. With the advent of technology, GIS is now used to accurately determine spatial information for flood hazard maps.

This study greatly contributed to the following:

1. Localizing GIS technology

Localizing technology contributes to closing the digital gap between those who have easy access to technology and those who do not. The importance of empowering local communities also provides a holistic approach to fully participate in addressing development problems in society.

2. Promote the importance of a bottom-up approach

In addressing development problems, it is important to provide a people-based solution so that all persons of concern can participate in developing common goals and actions.

3. Provide a plan for community-based disaster preparedness

The Philippines is constantly visited by typhoons every year yet the country's disaster preparedness and management plans fail to keep up with modern technology. Another way to unburden the national agencies is to create programs that include community-based interventions to address disaster response.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study only covered the flood-prone urban areas of Davao City specifically two barangays adjacent to each other where purok-based disaster response teams are present. These communities are located beside the Davao River which causes floods, especially during the rainy season from November to January. Before, the Davao River Basin was said to overflow once every five years but instances like what happened during Typhoon Vinta in 2017 proved otherwise. The city government declared a state of calamity after 25 villages and 18,500 families were affected by the storm (Adel, 2017). As a result, communities initiated their own activities for flood mitigation such as planting *malibago* or sea rosemallow trees along the riverbanks. The study focused on the impact of visual communication in the development of GIS-based flood hazard maps. Optimal templates for flood hazard maps are also determined with the community to highlight the importance of localization of technology down to the grassroots level.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Participatory mapping Using Geographic Information System

Geographic Information System (GIS) is a framework used for gathering, storing, and processing spatial data that can be used to visualize maps. The term “Geographical Information System” was coined by the researchers of Man Machine Interaction at MIT but was visualized successfully on monitors in the early 1990s. Originally, GIS applications were used by specialists who have already knowledge on manipulating spatial data. Now, common people regularly use GIS applications. With the integration of web and GIS applications opportunities for inexperienced users arise to look at maps over the Internet (Khan & Adnan, 2010).

There are various GIS software that are readily available for anyone interested in using the technology in community development. Perhaps the most notable GIS software application is ArcGIS with cutting-edge features enabling its users to produce maps that have expandable features. However, the software is expensive for other organizations to legally purchase so despite its promising features, ArcGIS is usually substituted with Quantum GIS (QGIS). QGIS is a free and open-source cross-platform desktop GIS application that supports viewing, editing, and analysis of geospatial data (QGIS, 2013). The software can be easily downloaded and installed on any computer processing unit such as Mac, Windows, and Linux to start the mapping process.

With its capability to handle different types of information, GIS can be used in any field that requires acquiring the exact location of a specific population. Studies have shown the effectiveness of using GIS software. For example, McLafferty and Grady (2005) studied the geographic distribution of women's health services provided by urban, community-based free clinics. GIS data revealed substantial gaps in healthcare access among various racial/ethnic groups. Once the information was shared, community clinics reallocated their resources to reach more of the surrounding population.

When community-based organizations operating in under-resourced communities are given access to user-friendly data, they are better able to use the information to make evidence-based decisions for program planning. Aronson et al. (2007) tested this concept in a community assessment addressing infant mortality, using GIS mapping to gather data and engage residents in the health initiative. GIS mapping enabled the researchers to produce more accessible and understandable information for the residents.

In disaster management, GIS enables carrying out complex tasks to assess the situation and provide evidence-based solutions to address policy changes. The software is already considered as a tool to support the decision-making process with local government units and civil society organizations. As a matter of fact, GIS is already used for financial, security, and agricultural purposes in the country. In terms of marketing and retail, investors use maps to determine the ideal space for a new establishment with consideration to the accessibility and convenience of the location. In the field of science and technology, GIS is also used to map forest cover, water

sources, and even rare animal sightings which helps produce a clear picture of the importance of maintaining our protected areas.

A study conducted by Huu Ty et al. (2006) integrated GIS into environmental planning in A Loui which covers the watershed area in Central Vietnam. A participative method in the context of climate change was tested due to its increasing problems with landslides and erosions. The process of creating a map included a consultation with the affected communities and local authorities to combine the top-down and bottom-up approaches. Indigenous knowledge was also taken into consideration with the GIS model building to include the most appropriate location for agricultural lands. A few consultations with the local authorities were also made to ensure the accuracy of the secondary data about the community. The methodology employed by the researchers addressed the criticisms usually received by studies on environmental planning which is the lack of local ownership and being heavily reliant on external scientific datasets.

Participatory mapping can also be empowering for the communities involved. A similar study by Fox et al. (2006) concluded that spatial information provided by maps can enable the community to manage resources, monitor development projects, and resolve conflicts on their own. The study had a larger scope by interviewing 23 participants from non-government organizations, project staff members, and university researchers who extensively used GIS while doing fieldwork. The representatives had different backgrounds from Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, and the United States. Communities that became the subject of the study were taught mapping through a handheld GPS device which is the most convenient way of localizing the technology. As a matter of fact, the mapping process helped to recognize the indigenous rights in the

Philippines when the Higa-onons in Impasug-ong, Bukidnon finally settled their 10,054.88 hectares ancestral domain claim. As documented by Abeto et al. (2004), a number of community members were taught to use handheld GPS devices as they collected coordinates from their domain. After the data gathering, a three-dimensional model was made wherein the community had the opportunity to include sacred places, mountains, rivers, and cultural sites that are important to preserve their tradition. The GIS-based maps played a vital role in negotiations with local authorities to finally award the Higa-onons their Certificate of Ancestral Domain Claim due to the accurate visual representation provided by the maps.

Participatory mapping projects can be categorized under six broad themes: 1) to articulate and communicate spatial knowledge to outsiders; 2) to record and archive local knowledge; 3) for land-use planning and resource management; 4) to advocate for change; 5) to increase capacity within communities; and 6) to address-resource related conflict (Corbett, 2009). The growth of participatory mapping approaches only signifies that the power is slowly shifting to non-experts. People at the grassroots level get to have first-hand experience in addressing development problems that their local communities face daily. Rather less documented, however, is the fact that GIS maps can be more user-friendly than other forms of data presentation, helping community-based organizations understand community data and facilitating a better understanding of the community. The result should be programs that can better address community needs (Aronson et.al., 2007).

GIS Use in Disaster Management

A disaster is defined as a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society causing widespread human, material, economic, or environmental

losses that exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources (ISDR, 2003). According to Mansurian et.al., (2005), disasters interrupt society by claiming lives, creating victims, and destroying infrastructures and houses. When a disaster occurs, funds and budgets that have been assigned for development purposes are diverted to respond to that disaster and return quality of life to normal. Disasters also have negative impacts on the environment as they affect natural resources. Therefore, considering society, economy, and environment as the three main components of sustainable development, disasters have a negative impact on sustainable development which makes appropriate management of disasters a necessity.

Many countries abroad are already utilizing GIS to address various disaster management issues. GIS can be extremely beneficial in emergency response tactics, but using this data to manage these disasters is just as important. Disaster management is based on plans, analysis, and actions. Governments, communities, and companies use spatial analysis to analyze and aid first-response teams. This is used to prevent deaths and damage while getting a kickstart on assisting communities to get back to regularity (USGS, 2021). GIS tools can be also used more effectively in the management of natural disasters as they can illustrate dynamically all the available data, showing real-time aspects of the impending dangers (Yao et al., 2011). In this frame, they can be used to support the decision-making process in the operation centers and at the same time to inform citizens about the current situation (Kuchеров et al., 2017).

A study conducted by Nefros et al. (2022) revealed that GIS is used in smart cities to reduce the impact of natural disasters. However, their increasing complexity and the impacts of climate crisis, have rendered them extremely vulnerable to

natural disasters. As it was revealed, GIS and remote sensing can integrate the results of existing and novel scientific methods, applied for each phase of the natural disasters' management. Moreover, as it was shown, they can provide these results through easily understandable maps and interactive web tools, which can be combined under a common platform, which is nowadays easily accessible either from a personal computer or a mobile device. Thus, they provide the necessary framework for a natural disaster's successful management and at the same time for the effective diffusion of the generated knowledge. Hence, they contribute to the enhancement of safety and the effective administration of smart cities in the sector of civil protection.

Due to its geographical and geological conditions, Taiwan suffers from many natural hazards which often cause serious damage to property and even life losses. Hence, the country's National Science and Technology Center for Disaster Reduction (NCDR) employs advanced telecommunications and information technologies to enhance its capabilities to collect and analyze information about hazards and distribute timely instructions. These include basic maps, real-time information on typhoons and rainfall issued by the Central Weather Bureau, real-time water information from the Water Resources Agency, and the hazard maps indicating areas of potential landslide, debris flow, and flooding made by NCDR herself to estimate endangered areas under the current typhoon (Hsu & Lin, 2005).

A case study carried out in Turrialba, Costa Rica used an orthophoto method in which all buildings, land parcels, and roads within the city and its direct surroundings were digitized resulting in a digital parcel map for which a number of hazard and vulnerability attributes were collected in the field. Based on historical information a GIS database was generated, which was used to generate flood depth

maps for different return periods. The resulting database serves as an important tool in the disaster preparedness phase of disaster management at the municipal level (Westin et al., 2002). The study was sponsored by UNESCO to produce a multi-hazard risk assessment of the city since it is prone to landslides, flooding, and earthquakes.

In 2014, Typhoon Yolanda hit the Philippines which was thought to be the most devastating typhoon that made landfall in history. The storm surge that occurred during Yolanda cost properties and lives due to the miscommunication behind the phenomenon. As a matter of fact, some locals did not understand what storm surge meant and even wrongly referred to as tsunami. According to a study conducted by GIZ, a German development agency, the official storm surge hazard map underestimated the inundation area of the storm surge. The actual area was larger and close to the inundation area of the official tsunami hazard maps (Neussner, 2014). At that time, the hazard maps did not consider the fact that storm surges can reach up to seven meters in length despite numerous warning forecasts of PAGASA. Even the designated evacuation areas were flooded caused by the unforeseen impact of the surge that wiped away properties. GIZ found out that almost 94% of deaths were caused by the storm surge and could have been avoided if the coastal communities had been prepared for the typhoon. There were GIS-based maps available which could have greatly helped the evacuation process during the first 72 hours before the typhoon made landfall, but the maps were not utilized due to the lack of appreciation in the software.

Localizing technology has played a huge part when it comes to the process of closing the digital gap that continues to widen as new innovations in technology develop over time. In the digital age where information is already a commodity,

people are expected to develop skills in digital literacy to fully adapt to a dynamic society. However, adapting to a digital society is also about having access to the Internet and owning gadgets such as tablets, laptops, and smartphones. According to Cova (2016), the level of GIS activity in emergency management may be increasing, but in the eyes of the emergency management community, GIS has a long way to go to meet their needs. Numerous challenges still exist in the application of GIS in this area, as well as many of its related fields like hazard mitigation.

In GIS mapping, a study conducted by Zarcadoolas, et al. (2014) revealed that a majority of adults who have not completed high school could not read or use the maps for basic and vital information which includes identifying if they lived in a hurricane evacuation zone and locating the nearest evacuation center. The map used in the study was a visual representation of the entire Harlem District with designated safe zones and degree hazards in specific locations. Data was collected through a cross-sectional survey by asking questions related to the knowledge attained by examining the level of understanding of the participants when presented with an evacuation map.

There is a growing popularity for the use of GIS in various fields but there is little research about the public receiving information in the form of GIS data. Typical GIS map layouts look complicated with no corresponding narratives in the local language to further explain the map. The maps are frequently used as a method of constructing an argument or illustrating alternatives in a decision faced by a community. Given that 50% of the adult population reads at the 8th grade level or lower (NAAL, 2003). Information is often archived in the database of concerned agencies and seldom reaches the communities that are vulnerable to disasters. Printed maps are available but are usually posted in barangay halls instead of

cascading information to the grassroots level to help them prepare in the event of a disaster.

Disaster Management in Local Communities

The Philippines is located along the typhoon belt which is visited by an average of 20 typhoons every year. To address the pressing issue of disasters, Republic Act 10121, or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction Act (PDRRM) Act was passed into law in 2010. The law includes a holistic and integrated approach to lessening the impacts of disasters through the involvement of all stakeholders, especially local communities throughout the entire process. A community-based disaster reduction effort is most successful when it involves the direct participation of the people most likely to be exposed to the hazards—in the planning, decision-making, and operational activities at all levels of responsibility (Zubir & Amirrol, 2011). Key leaders at the grassroots level are encouraged to play a vital role when it comes to protecting their own communities in times of emergency.

Under the PDRRM Act, a Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (DRRMO) is required in every province, city, and municipality and a Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction Management Council in every barangay (BDRRMC). The BDRRMC is divided into sub-committees namely: Warning, Rescue, Evacuation, Disaster Relief, Medical, Fire Brigade, Damage Control, Security, Supply, Transportation, and Communication. Within this process, the formation and strengthening of a community disaster response organization or community disaster management volunteer team is the key to mobilizing communities for sustainable disaster risk reduction (Victoria, 2003). Creating a functional BDRRMC provides a

channel for both government and non-government organizations (NGOs) to assist the community in improving their disaster protocols.

There are numerous initiatives to promote community-based approaches to disaster management. United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction assisted the Citizen's Disaster Response Network which is composed of grassroots and national NGOs conducting campaigns and advocacy work on capacity building to mitigate the impacts of disasters.

In July 1995, one of the network members conducted a three-day training course on disaster response at the community level. Emerging from this course, community members formulated an evacuation plan and designed a warning system to monitor the lava flow of Mount Pinatubo during monsoon season (UNISDR, 2004). Getting the community involved in disaster management practices has its own set of advantages and challenges as well. A study conducted by Matthies (2017) looked at the development and structure of the *purok* system in San Francisco, Cebu in the field of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR).

The *purok* is the subdivision of a barangay and thus signifies a sub-village in the Philippines (Allen, 2003). One advantage of establishing a *purok* system in DRR is to encourage the concept of social cohesion at the smallest unit of governance. Social cohesion involves building shared values and communities of interpretation, reducing disparities in wealth and income, and generally enabling people to have a sense that they are engaged in a common enterprise, facing shared challenges and that they are members of the same community (Maxwell, 1996).

Promoting community-based approaches in coming up with solutions to address development problems encourages people to work towards a common goal.

However, one of the challenges presented in implementing a *purok* system is the maintenance of the organization dedicated to responding to DRR concerns. One of the challenges is the inactivity of the members due to time-consuming jobs that get in the way of attending monthly meetings. Another concern is the people who lose interest in the system therefore leaving behind their duties and responsibilities. Lastly, other members refuse to participate in activities caused by political positions against government representatives in the local government units.

In the field of participatory mapping, there are limited resources with local communities as subjects of the study. Most of the participatory mapping research studies are related to ancestral domain promotion in indigenous people's territories. In a paper by Daguitan (2013), a number of Kalanguya communities in the municipality of Tinoc, Ifugao province made three-dimensional models using Google Maps. They identified seven uses for the land use map that they created with the assistance of partner civil society organizations. The study highlighted the importance of capacity building to further promote the bottom-up approach when it comes to community development.

Maps as Communication Tools

Maps have always been made; they may have been one of the first forms of human communication. Maps exist in many forms, can represent different ideas, and are used for many purposes. In choosing what to represent, how to represent it, and what not to represent, maps are expressions of power (Cochrane et al., 2014). Poole (1995) highlighted that maps have always been symbols and instruments of power. Going back in history, maps were used by the powerful to assert control over territorial boundaries. Even participatory mapping is not new since members of the

community have always made lines in the sand and drawings on the wall to create a visual representation of their resources. However, with the advent of technology, mapping has been utilized for a myriad of different purposes. Whereas traditional mapping represented the top-down, authoritarian, centrist paradigm wherein experts produce maps used by individuals and communities, the new world of mapping includes a constant creation of information, flowing in multiple directions, from anyone who wishes to contribute it (Goodchild, 2007). Although barriers such as digital access still exist, modern technology paved the way to challenge the norm of creating maps.

Community-based and participatory mapping, because of the possibility for it to transform power, has been advocated as a means to foster inclusive, democratic empowerment (Lydon, 2002). However, in order for an initiative to be fully inclusive, map layouts should be presented in a way that even the general public can use it, especially in times of disaster. The preparation of graphic design in maps is like that of a written communication, they must each be planned carefully so that the reader will be able to obtain as easily as possible, the information being conveyed (Dhamija & Sood, 2010). Map reading is a complex process, in which people construct meaning by interpreting the various visual representations within the context of their information needs, goals, knowledge, and experience. Visual design of the map and the characteristics of the hazard map audience can therefore influence how hazard maps are understood and applied (Thompson, 2017). Creating visual maps and information materials for local communities to identify the specific locations for evacuation centers and households that might be affected during floods is the goal of this research.

Understanding the Importance of Visual Rhetoric in Design

Since the 1980s, scholars have been analyzing the rhetoric of design as a means of communicating with audiences (Buchanan, 1985; Kinross, 1985; Kress and van Leeuwen, 1996). Design is always rhetorical whether done purposefully by the designer or not. According to Kress and van Leeuwen, the analysis of images and textual design together can help analyze the impact of a material on its intended audience. Any images used are meant to complement the text and provide additional insight into the concepts of the material.

In their study, Firmansyah et al. (2021) discussed that the key to the rhetorical perspective on the image and what sets it apart from others is the rhetorical perspective of focusing on the rhetorical response of the image rather than the aesthetic. In rhetorical responses, on the contrary, meaning is associated with images. The colors, lines, textures, and rhythms in the image provide the basis for visitors to infer the image, emotions, and ideas in the image. The focus of that visual rhetoric perspective is on understanding the rhetorical response of the image.

Visual rhetoric has long been used particularly in the field of advertising, marketing, and social campaigns. Waller (2012) discussed how changes in layout, for example in redesigned documents such as articles enable users to adopt particular reading strategies and may clarify confusion by providing accurate information. Similarly, improving the layout of the graphics can also help in visual articulation and making information accessible in a glance. Although Kostelnick (1990) suggests that users' at-a-glance impressions are often undervalued, an

increasing number of studies suggest that 'good' design has benefits for both usability and rhetoric.

Larson and colleagues (Larson and Picard 2005; Larson, Hazlett et al. 2006; Hazlett, Larson et al. 2008; Larson 2010) explore whether conventions associated with 'good' typography influence users' perception of documents and a reader's ability to perform cognitive tasks. Their research suggests that: 'A well-designed page is more likely to be impactful and cause the reader to act on the message' (Larson, 2010). Additionally, Black and Stanbridge (2012) found evidence to support the premise that users' impressions of visual design influenced their assumptions about how easy information was to understand in a range of everyday documents received by mail. This study reveals the 'combined aesthetic and functional impact of document design and its capacity either to facilitate interaction between the initiating organization and the user or, conversely, to deliver a negative experience.'

Visual Communication Design of Disaster-related Materials

People interpret abstract meanings from colors, which makes color a useful perceptual feature for visual communication. This process is complicated, however, because there is seldom a one-to-one correspondence between colors and meanings (Schloss et al., 2018). In DRR, the colors red, yellow, and orange are a staple when it comes to interpreting the risk levels in times of flood. Accordingly, visual map products have been found to improve comprehension of hazard information when compared to non-visual communication formats like tables and charts (Severtson & Vatovec, 2012).

Since seeing precedes reading, the reader's first glance influences the information processing that follows. The balanced arrangement of visual elements on

the page, the contrast among these elements, and the efficient use of space – together create a unified visual display that predisposes the reader to respond strategically to the information in the document. Such responses are often dismissed as subjective and impressionistic, but they must be regarded as intrinsic to the rhetoric of the document (Kostelnick, 1990). Exploring different designs requires consultations with the community in order to come up with a participatory approach to the design. Further, map designs that are aesthetically appealing or intuitively preferred by map makers and users are not necessarily the most effective for decision-making tasks (Hegarty et al., 2010).

Chapter III

FRAMEWORKS

Theoretical Lens

Visual communicators solve complex problems through the use of visual language. In order for visual text to be efficient, the message and placement must be strategic depending on the purpose of the material. Even pictures must be properly placed in order for the message to be clear and concise. With the rapid advancement in technology, there is a plethora of visual images that are present on social media websites such as Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube.

The theory that was used for this study is Visual Rhetoric by Sonja K. Foss. Visual rhetoric is the term used to describe the study of visual imagery within the discipline of rhetoric. As a branch of knowledge, rhetoric dates to classical Greece and is concerned with the study of the use of symbols to communicate (Foss, 2005). The field of visual rhetoric is relatively new despite the fact that the theory has already been used for centuries. Visual rhetoric falls under the category of visual literacy which is defined as the ability to read, analyze, and evoke meaning from visual text through the means of visual grammar. Elements of visual language include typefaces, color, page structure, photographs, illustrations, graphs, and charts (Kress et al., 2006).

Rhetoric is considered the art of persuasion which motivates and informs the audience. Kenneth Burke, a rhetorical theorist, helped pave the way for the emergence of visual rhetoric. Kostelnick and Roberts (1998) suggested a few questions to consider for visual communicators: 1) Is the message intended to inform

or persuade, or is it a call to action?; 2) Who is the message directed to?; 3) What is the purpose of the document and where will it be viewed? There are three components to a rhetorical situation: audience, purpose, and context. These components would greatly affect the colors, text, and overall layout of the page.

The audience is the viewer in which the material is directed. Identifying and even segmenting the audience further can ensure that the message is being delivered effectively. For the study, the audience is the residents of Barangay 10-A and Purok 27 Riverside in Ma-a, Davao City. The mentioned communities are located along the Davao River which makes them prone to landslides and flooding. Both barangays have their own peculiarities that can affect their interpretations of the flood hazard maps. Understanding the audience's needs can lead to deepening the purpose of the study. The material should inspire or inform the viewer of a new concept or persuade them to act, feel, or think in a particular way (Kostelnick & Roberts, 1998). In this case, the purpose of the study is to identify the ideal templates preferred by the residents in designing GIS-based flood hazard maps. Visual rhetoric is used to specify the placement, typography, and images that are vital elements in the map.

Human experiences that are spatially oriented, non-linear, multidimensional, and dynamic often can be communicated only through visual imagery or other non-discursive symbols (Foss, 2005). Spatial data are interpreted through maps which are then used for various reasons such as emergency response. Localizing maps promotes empowerment by encouraging participation at the community level. Complex tools and a lack of resources can often get in the way of mapping programs which inhibits the community from participating. Through localization, the community members were able to identify important elements to be included in the map.

Chapter IV

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a qualitative design through a phenomenological approach to identify the insights of purok members on the ideal templates for GIS-based flood hazard maps. Phenomenology examines human insights through the descriptions provided by the people involved which is similar to the research questions this study seeks to answer. With the use of visual rhetoric, the residents from flood-prone areas in Davao City can provide feedback on the template that is found most effective for them. Qualitative methods such as key informant interviews with key leaders and focus group discussions with the community members helped the researcher in determining the ideal templates for the maps.

Locale of the Study

Davao River can be traced back to the mountainous areas of San Fernando, Bukidnon with the major portion being in Davao City. It flows southward meandering through the city and eventually emptying out into the Davao Gulf. Out of 182 barangays in Davao, almost 40 are vulnerable to floods, especially during the rainy season. Two areas that are situated along the riverbanks were significantly impacted during the onslaught of Typhoon Vinta in December 2017. This incident persuaded the residents to form a community-centered disaster response team to alleviate the burden of their respective local government units.

Sampling/Procedure

In this study, the researcher based the population sample from the most affected barangays during the past typhoons that ravaged Davao City. The data was obtained in coordination with the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office. Both barangays are already active in disaster response training programs organized by CDRRMO and other civil society organizations. The respondents for data collection were drawn from specific residential areas within two different barangays. The purok selection process was conducted through consultations held with their respective local officials. Both puroks were selected because of their proximity to the river and past damage brought about by typhoons.

Variable Specification

The respondents for this study were the residents of the high-risk communities in Davao City. The barangays that were included in the study are identified by the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office as two of the flood-prone barangays in Davao City. Since the study only focuses on the optimum design templates for digital-based maps, the respondents are considered as the message designers with the produced map as the message. Following the theory of visual rhetoric, the components of rhetoric are purpose, audience, and context which were also considered in the study.

Data Collection

The participants involved in the study were members of the community-centered disaster teams from two flood-prone barangays in the city. To determine the preferred layout for localized digital maps, the steps in data collection are as follows:

Document Review

In coordination with CDRRMO, the list of barangays and puroks to be included in the study was thoroughly reviewed and validated. After identifying the puroks, courtesy letters for the barangays were given out to follow the standard process at the community level. Collaborating with the Purok Disaster Action Team volunteers will follow after the requirements for the barangay are approved.

Key Informant Interviews (KIIs)

After reviewing the documents, the researcher proceeded to conduct KIIs. The respondents were the residents of the two puroks together with PDAT members. Specific details about their preferred layout and interpretation of flood hazard maps emerged during the interviews such as identifying elements and language to be used.

Data Processing and Analysis

The processing followed as soon as the KIIs with community members were done. Data gathered from field interviews about the preferred template were considered in creating a localized layout for the GIS-based flood hazard maps.

Additional concerns such as the type of IEC material to be used for the maps were also noted. Flood hazard maps were sourced from the City Planning and Development Office (CPDO) through their GIS specialists. Collected data from the field were then incorporated into the making of the localized layout for the GIS-based flood hazard maps. The output was presented to the community along with copies of the maps.

Ethical Considerations

Before proceeding with the data collection and analysis, the researcher secured letters to conduct interviews with community members. Coordinating with the barangay is important to ensure that the researcher is safe while gathering data. Respondents were also asked to sign a consent form if they agreed to take part in the study. All confidentiality agreements were honored by the researcher.

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to local historians, the name *Davao* came from the *Bagobo* word *davoh* which referred to the Davao River, an essential lifeline for the tribe. To the *Bagobo*, the word *davoh* also means “a place beyond the high grounds,” alluding to the settlements located at the mouth of the Davao River, where they bartered their forest goods (Hearne, et.al., 2008). The city has eight (8) major watersheds, but the Davao River Watershed (DRW) ranks number one in almost all key demographic indicators such as population alienable and disposable land, degraded timberland, built-up areas, general commercial zone, conservation zone, cultivated areas, closed canopy, grassland, and banana plantations. The DRW is the largest watershed in the city which covers about 50% of the total land area at 121,385 hectares within the boundary of the city and 175,776 hectares in total area including some municipalities in the province of Bukidnon.

Incidentally, 40% of the population of Davao City lives close to the watershed with a majority of the households clustered around the urban mouth of the river. Multiple hazards affect the population within the watershed which include severe flooding, especially during monsoon season with 90 out of the 113 barangays being located in areas with medium to high risk of flooding. According to a study conducted by the Disaster Risk and Exposure Assessment for Mitigation (DREAM) Program, Davao River used to overflow every 10 years causing massive floods to its nearby communities. However, since the start of 2017, it has been noted that the river now floods every four to five years which poses a serious risk to Davaoeños.

Flooding, viewed as the most threatening and likely among the hazards affecting the select communities in the DRW has the same geophysical route characteristics and predictions as manifested by (a) Tropical Storm *Sendong* in the Lanao del Sur-Iligan City watershed, in the Bukidnon-Cagayan de Oro City watershed on 16 December 2011, (b) by Tropical Storm *Pablo* in Compostela Valley watershed in 3 December 2012, and (c) Tropical Storm *Vinta* in Davao Oriental on 20 December 2017.

Emergency response and coping measures currently being employed by the communities include rudimentary monitoring by some residents of the rising water level and accompanying turbidity, monitoring of weather forecasts on the radio or television, and house-to-house warnings during evacuations. However, timely evacuation of the residents remains to be a big challenge. With the support of their local barangay and the city government, the residents decided to organize a Purok Disaster Action Team (PDAT) to respond in times of emergency situations in their own communities.

Community Profile of Purok A

According to the community master list, there are currently 96 existing households in the area since newer settlers are required to reside at least six months in the area before being considered part of the community. Purok A is largely populated by Muslim settlers with a majority of the residents relying on jobs like selling, driving tricycles, and working on the construction of the gabion right beside the river. Gabion is a structure often made with rocks and concrete caged within a wirework container found in riverbanks for erosion control.

Figure 1.

Gabion found in Purok A used as an improvised water level indicator.

The construction of the gabion was widely disputed by the community members of Purok A since several of the residents will be displaced to give way to the structure. Despite the dialogue raised by the community, the city government continued to build the gabion along the river easement. However, on the 20th of December 2017, the river continued swelling up despite the sunny weather forecast until it overflowed onto the unfinished gabion which flooded the entire area.

Figure 2.

A severely damaged house during TS Vinta at Purok A.

According to an active PDAT youth member of the community, they were informed by the PDAT personnel coming from the upland areas that the water level is rapidly increasing which might flood the downstream urban areas. After receiving the text message, PDAT members of Purok A actively roamed the area informing the residents to prepare for evacuation. Before the water even rushed toward the community, people were already safely gathered at the covered court while waiting for the rescue trucks that would transport them to an elementary school which is also the nearest evacuation center.

During the evacuation, PDAT members noted that their hand-drawn community map was used to locate residents who were not yet present at the covered court. Since the members already had a master list, they simply triangulated the data and discovered that there were still residents who refused to leave their homes. The PDAT members immediately arrived at the scene and convinced the

residents to flee rather than wait for the flood to rush in. Fortunately, there were no casualties in the purok due to community initiative.

Lived Experiences of Purok A

During the interview, the researcher managed to gather four PDAT responders aged 56, 42, 54, and 23. According to the tribal leader of the community, during the onslaught of Typhoon Vinta, the immediate response of the PDAT members was commendable.

Kadtong December, daghang balay ang nangaanod. Unya nag dugang pa gyud sila og pahibalo nga ang mga tao daw sa bukid, namakwit na tanan. Kadto nga time, ang tubig ni-level na diri sa sapa. Ingon pa ang communication sa mga PDAT sa taas, kung unsa kadako dira ang tubig niabot dira sa inyoha, muabotay pa ang triple. Kaluy-an sa Ginoo ato, wala pa nisulod ang tubig, ang mga tao namakwit na.

(Last December, several houses were washed out by the flood. They also informed us that the residents in the uplands already evacuated. During that time, the floodwater was already of the same height as the river. According to other PDAT members from rural upland communities, the water level may triple its height. By God's mercy, the residents evacuated even before the water rushed in.)

One of the respondents who immediately informed the residents about the possibility of severe flooding was the purok leader of the community. According to him, the swift response to the situation coupled with the assistance of the map saved their lives.

Isip purok leader, obligasyon nako nga ingnan ang komunidad nga kinahanglan na mangandam inig mutaas na ang tubig sa sapa. Kadtong Vinta, ang amoang mapa ang pinakaimportanteng butang nga among nagamit. Pinaagi sa mapa, dali ra namo ma-identify kung kinsa ang among kinahanglan pa i-rescue.

(As a purok leader, it is my obligation to inform the community when to prepare for evacuation when the water level starts to rise. During Vinta, our map played a vital role in our responsibility. With the map, we easily identified the households that we needed to rescue.)

The PDAT assistant leader recalled the unexpected turn of events during the onslaught of the typhoon last December. He added that the landscape drastically changed in just a span of an hour. However, with the help of the map, they quickly identified evacuation routes within the community to avoid congestion in major walkways.

Pwera hinumdom atong Vinta, pirti gyud kapasas sa panghitabo. Giradyohan ra mi sa mga PDAT gikan sa taas nga grabe na daw kataas ang tubig didto. Tingala mi nga hayag man kaayo atong adlawa pero nituo gihapon mi. Maayo na lang, magkaila ra mi tanan diri so dali ra mi natapok. Amo dayon gigamit tong mapa aron ma-identify namo ang mga agianan para dili magtapok sa tunga sa kalsada ang mga tao.

(I remembered that during Vinta, everything happened so fast. The PDAT members from the upland areas transmitted a radio message informing us that the water level from the headwaters is rapidly rising. We were confused because as far as I can remember, that was a sunny day. But since we trust

them, we are obliged to evacuate. Fortunately, we already know each other within the community so it was relatively easy to convene. Using the map, we identified the evacuation routes people can take in order to avoid congestion and traffic on the main roads.)

An active member of the PDAT Youth recalled how she got the communication from the upland community since she was stationed at the office at that time. Despite being the youngest respondent during the interview, she carefully recounted the events leading up to the evacuation up until the moment that they had to return to the purok to convince the others who had not yet evacuated to proceed to the covered court.

Naa ko sa office atong time nga nag radyo ang mga PDAT sa bukid nga gataas na daw ang tubig sa ilaha. Pag copy nako sa radyo, nidagan dayon ko padulong sa balay sa PDAT assistant leader para i-relay sa iyaha akong nadunggan. Pila ra ka minuto nilabay, nagtapok na mi tanan PDAT responders didto sa opisina aron masabotan ang evacuation routes gamit ang mapa.

Nigamit na si purok leader og megaphone ug bagting aron ma-inform ang mga tao nga mubakwit na. Kadtong pagbakwit, nagihapanay man didto sa covered court, nasakpan tong mga wala pa pinaagi sa mapa. Dayon giadtuan sila sa ilang mga balay aron pugson mag evacuate. Ang uban sa ilaha wala pa nakaandam og “go bag” mao to medyo nadugay pero nakalingkawas ra man tanan.

(I was at the office at the time when I received a radio transmission from the PDAT members upland that the water is increasing. After I responded to the

message, I immediately ran to the PDAT assistant leader's house to relay the information. Minutes passed and all the PDAT responders of the community gathered at the office to identify the evacuation routes with the help of the map.

The purok leader roamed the community using the megaphone and alarm system to tell the residents to start evacuating. During the evacuation process, we were setting up the map when we realized that there were still residents who refused to leave their homes. The responders quickly ran to their homes and convinced them to evacuate. Some of them did not have their go bags prepared so it took quite a long time but thankfully everyone was safe.)

Preferred Guidelines in Determining GIS Information of Purok A

Prior to designing the GIS maps, the researcher conducted an interview with the PDAT members of Purok A to determine their preferred guidelines for writing and designing GIS information. All four of the respondents have prior knowledge about the concept of GIS since they were already familiar with the maps given by CPDO. In 2019, the PDAT was also tapped to assist in gathering data within their community which will be fed into the software to process GIS-based maps.

According to the tribal leader, the geotagging of locations within their purok was not an easy feat because the houses were relatively close to each other. Although he was not a part of the data collection team, all organizations and government agencies who intend to operate in their purok would pass through him for approval. Hence, he was already given a short introduction to the importance of using satellite-based data.

Since ako ang tribal leader, ang mga proyekto nga gina propose sa mga NGO o sa gobyerno, gaagi usa sa akoo. Pag inform sa akoo nga magkuha daw sila og data diri sa community, siyempre kinahanglan usa nako mabal-an kung unsa ang proseso. Naglisod sila ato nga time kay dikit dikit lagi ang kabalayan diri sa amo.

Kaning GIS, pamilyar na ko ani kay tungod sa CPDO. Nianha sila diri ug naghatag og mapa. Karon, paglantaw nako sa mapa, barangay level man ang sakop. Di kaayo makuha ang purok. Isip usa ka tribal leader, importante para nako nga maapil ang among kultura which is ang mosque ug among madrasa.

(Since I am the tribal leader, all the projects proposed by NGOs and government agencies will have to go through me. When they informed me that they were going to collect data here in the community, of course, I had to know about the process. They had a hard time since the houses were too close to each other.

I am already familiar with the concept of GIS because of CPDO. They paid a visit to the community and gave us a map. Now when I took a closer look, the map only covers the barangay level; not the purok. As a tribal leader myself, I think that it is important that we highlight a part of our culture which are the mosque and madrasa.)

For him, an important aspect that needs to be included in the GIS information of their purok are the mosque and madrasah which, according to him, are often left out. Since they are the only Muslim community residing in the area, he felt the need to uphold their Islamic customs to pass them on to the younger generation.

Kani akong concern dili ko sigurado kung parehas ba mi diri tanan og huna-huna. Pero para sa akua, isip usa ka Muslim, ako gatuong kinahanglan gyud ipakita sa atong community map ning mosque ug madrasah. Kami ra man gud diri sa barangay ang purely Muslim community mao importante na nako. Nakasinati na sad mi og diskriminasyon sa among pila ka tuig nga pagpuyo diri mao pinakaimportante gyud nga ipadayon ang among mga tinuohan.

(My main concern is, although I am not sure if everyone here in the group shares the same sentiment. But for me, as a Muslim, I firmly believe that we must put the mosque and madrasah on the map. This is important to me since we are the only Muslim community in our barangay. We also experienced discrimination after years of residing here, so we need to uphold our customs and traditions now more than ever.)

As for the active PDAT respondents, their concern is mostly linked to the evacuation routes and flood-prone areas within the purok. According to the purok leader, his priority is on determining the accurate location of the roads that the community can use during evacuation.

Para sa akua, akong napansin atong nagbagyo diri, medyo naglisod pa ang mga tao kung aha gyud among mga dalan nga gina-consider nga evacuation route. Importante man gud para sa amoa, mga rescuer, nga makita ang dagan sa tao kung aha mangagi.

(What I noticed during the typhoon was residents were having a hard time identifying the roads we consider as part of the evacuation route. As rescuers, it is important for us to determine the flow of people coming and going.)

As mentioned before by the tribal leader, the community is composed of households that are closely located to each other with narrow roads that can only accommodate two persons at a time. So, during emergencies, the concern of the purok leader is important in order to avoid congestion and even stampede. On the other hand, the concerns of other PDAT members were related to identifying the households that might be severely affected by heavy flooding.

According to a respondent, aside from determining the physical structures present within the purok, it is also vital to include a flood susceptibility map where the respondents can ascertain which households, they have to rescue first due to their history of being severely damaged during disasters.

Kadto ilang gipang ingon ganina, importante man gyud tuod to. Pero siguro importante sad nga atuang mahibal-an kung kay kinsa nga mga balay ang kanunay maigo inig naay bagyo. Siyempre mag depende kung kinsa ang pinakaduol sa sapa o kung kinsa tong mga naa sa medyo baba nga lugar banda.

(The details that were mentioned earlier were important, but I guess it is also important for us to know which households are severely affected during typhoons. Of course, this would depend on which households have the closest proximity to the river or those who are residing in low-lying areas.)

The PDAT youth member added that she agrees with the suggestion of the previous respondent to develop a flood susceptibility map for the purok because aside from it being used as a basis for relief and rescue, it can also be used to determine the history of disasters in a community.

Naga uyon ko sa giingon ni Kuya nga kinahanglan buhatan sad og flood susceptibility map ang community. Para sa akua, importante nga mabal-an pud ang history sa baha. Diri man gud sa amoa [ma'am] balik balik gyud ang mga balay nga grabe og damage inig naay bagyo.

(I agree with what Kuya said earlier about the importance of creating a flood susceptibility map of the community. For me, it is important to know the flood history. Here in our area [ma'am], there are really houses that repeatedly get severe damages during typhoons.)

To summarize the inputs from the respondents, Purok A wants to see the distinct features of their community such as the mosque and madrasah on the map in order to highlight the *Kalagan* culture. Due to the purok being the only predominantly Muslim community within the neighborhood, they felt that they needed to preserve their identity by including the structures that reflect their belief system.

Another vital input raised during the data collection process was the need for the responders to have solid evidence of the areas within the community that frequently get damaged during floods. This highlights the keen observation skills of the respondents that the water enters and exits only at specific areas within the purok. According to the accounts of the PDAT responders, they have tried to convince the households located near the river to relocate but failed every time due to the fact that they have already established their homes within the area.

Interpretation of Flood Hazard Maps

After conducting the interview with the respondents, the researcher created a GIS-based community base map of Purok A according to the data gathered on the

field. The digital maps were produced by feeding geopoints to the QGIS software which were gathered by the researcher with the assistance of several community members. The CPDO also helped with the production of shape files for the locale of the study easing the process of translating the data from the ground to the computer.

The map of Purok A shown below is the one presented to the respondents in order to determine their interpretations of GIS information.

Figure 3.
Community Base Map of Purok A produced using QGIS.

As presented in the map, the houses are widely scattered within the community with the highest concentration of residents being near the river. The features on the map visualize that the area is relatively flat which can contribute to the rapid movement of floodwaters especially when other factors such as poor drainage system is involved. This lack of natural gradient or topographical variation can cause water to spread out more horizontally rather than draining or flowing downhill swiftly.

Maps can also serve as highly informative and illustrative tools to reflect the culture of a community. Since Purok A is a predominantly Muslim community, the respondents wanted to include the madrasah and mosque which are important places where they gather and socialize. By visually presenting these elements on a map, it becomes a powerful tool to not only understand but also celebrate and preserve the unique cultural identity of a community.

According to the purok leader, his first impression of the map was disorienting due to the fact that the houses do not form a straight line at all compared to their hand-drawn base map.

Pagkakita nako sa mapa [ma'am], natingala ko kay wala diay nakalinya ang mga balay diria; katag-katag gyud diay siya.

(When I validated the map [ma'am], I was surprised to see that the households in the community are not perfectly lined up; it is quite scattered).

The tribal leader added that he has not seen the community from an aerial perspective hence he was glad that the features shown on the map were the ones he suggested during the interview.

Nakauyon ko ani nga mapa kay klaro gyud ang mosque ug madrasah. Kaning mga ingon ani man gud nga butang, di namo makita sa mapa nga gihatag sa amoa sa gobyerno.

(I liked the map since the mosque and madrasah are present. We do not get to see these features with the maps given by the city government.)

Aside from the requested structures mentioned being present on the map, a respondent shared that the road features were ideal, especially in the event of

disasters. He added that the maps widely available for their perusal do not include major highways that are essential for evacuation and relief purposes.

Akong interpretasyon ani nga mapa kay dali ra siya masabtan. Klaro man ang mapa ug ang aduna sad siyay legend nga makita sa kilid. Ako, medyo edaran na man gyud ko, wala ko naglisod og sabot ani. Siguro akong na-appreciate og pag-ayo ani kay ang dalan nga makita nato didto sa taas banda. Ang mga dalan man gud maoy importante alang sa sipti nga pag bakwit ug pagluwas inig taas na ang tubig.

(My interpretation of the map is that it is easy to understand. The map is clear, and the legend is easily visible. Personally, I am old, but I did not have a hard time understanding the content of the map. Maybe what I appreciated the most was the presence of the road networks that can be found in the upper portion of the map. The roads are important for safety evacuation and relief when the water level is high.)

During a disaster, maps help in identifying critical locations such as shelters and roads that can ease access to those needing immediate assistance. This feature allows PDAT members to efficiently plan and deploy aid to affected areas. Maps are shared communication tools that facilitate collaboration among different agencies involved in disaster response. By using a common visual tool, stakeholders can communicate and coordinate efforts more effectively.

Following the request of the community to produce a flood susceptibility map, the initial data was sourced from the residents who experienced extreme flooding during Typhoon Vinta and triangulated with the data from CDRRMO. The image below is the produced flood susceptibility map for Purok A.

Figure 4.
Flood hazard map of Purok A produced using QGIS.

The lone youth respondent who requested a flood susceptibility map of their community appreciated the effort of going further into detail about the history of flooding in the area.

Ganahan ko ani nga mapa kay gipakita gyud kung aha dapit sa among purok ang grabe mabahaan. Dali ra sad sabton para sa akua [ma'am] nga ang colors nga gigamit kay blue ug green. Mas dali sabton nga ang blue nga parte maoy pinakagrabe bahaon unya ang green ug yellow, di kaayo.

(I like the map since it clearly depicts the areas within our purok that experiences severe flooding. It is easy to understand [ma'am], especially with the colors used which are blue and green. It is easier to understand that the

blue portion of the map is the one experiencing heavy flooding while the green and yellow areas, not so much.)

According to her, the records show that although the entire purok is flood-prone, it was only in 2017 that they experienced the worst in history with the onslaught of Typhoon Vinta. She shared that only the roofs were visible when they were rescued by the city government.

Flood susceptibility maps serve as proactive tools to mitigate risks and foster informed decision-making in efforts to minimize the impact of floods. These maps provide a visual representation of areas prone to flooding that allow authorities to identify high-risk zones. This awareness is key for preparedness efforts, enabling communities to plan ahead prior to an incoming tropical storm. Unfortunately, for Purok A, their most valued points of interest which are the mosque and madrasa, fall under moderate to high flood. Despite continuous efforts to convince the barangay to relocate the structures, they cannot afford to shoulder the construction costs.

Community Profile of Purok B

Purok B is located directly across Purok A which is previously mentioned as one of the subjects of this paper. The area is predominantly composed of residents who came from different barangays and decided to stay in Purok B as informal settlers. Despite the continuing land dispute with the city government, the community has one of the most proactive initiatives when it comes to environmental protection. Akin to the previous purok, the community also struggled with the construction of the gabion which displaced a number of residents in the area.

Figure 5.
Ongoing construction of gabion at Purok B.

The settlers organized the Protect the Davao River Movement (PDRM) People's Organization in 2009 to lead the establishment of plant nurseries and tree planting of malibago or sea rosemallow trees along the riverbank. The president of PDRM, who is also one of the respondents for the study, continues to oversee the progress of PDRM from its humble beginnings to being recognized by CENRO and DENR Region XI as their partner in promoting the importance of trees to prevent soil erosion, especially along riverbanks. Hence, the Brokenshire College of Davao adopted the community to benefit from their National Service Training Program (NSTP) wherein Purok B was given materials to build their own daycare center.

Figure 6.
Plant nursery at Purok B where they cultivate malibago.

Figure 7.
Pots of malibago at the nursery ready to be planted along the river.

Since the community garnered support from the local government units, their PDAT members have been trained to efficiently respond to disasters by the BDRRMO. Since the roll- out, an evacuation map and a database of community

member profiles were created. With consideration of senior citizens, people with disabilities, pregnant women and children, a contingency plan was put in place. Community members were equipped with knowledge and skills on how to respond to unexpected events.

The community also maximized the use of their own base map during the onslaught of TS Vinta. Similar to the experience of Purok A, the PDAT members of Purok B also used the map as basis to check the attendance of the evacuees especially those belonging in the vulnerable sectors. There were two senior citizens who were left inside their homes while everyone was busy evacuating. They were both immobile and had to be transported with a wheelchair going to the covered court.

Lived Experiences of Purok B

Purok B is one of the communities in Davao City that pioneered malibago tree planting along the riverbanks which is known to be good for soil stabilization. During the data collection process, the researcher gathered five PDAT respondents who put in effort in environmental protection aged 76, 54, 60, 23, and 25.

The aforementioned members were also the same set of PDAT members who responded during Typhoon Vinta. According to the PDRM president, the severe flooding during December 2017 was the scariest disaster he encountered during his 25-year stay in the community.

Kadtong nahitabo atong Vinta, mao siguro ang pinakahadlok nako nga nakita nga baha sa 25 years nga akong pagpuyo diri. Abi gyud nako mao na to ang katapusan sa among komunidad.

(The flooding brought about by Vinta was perhaps the scariest sight I ever had to witness in my 25 years of living in the community. I really thought that that would be the end for us.)

Another respondent agreed and even likened the flood to that of a washing machine since the water was reportedly spinning. Several debris from the upland areas were also rapidly cascading towards their houses.

Ang baha ato [ma'am] murag washing machine...kanang gatuyok-tuyok gani. Ang hadlok pud ato kay naay mga dagkong troso nga gipang-anod diri pasulod sa amoa.

(The movement of the flood was like a washing machine...it was spinning. I was also terrified because I saw huge logs heading towards us.)

They recalled that during the typhoon, there was still an unfinished portion of the gabion where the water rushed in. Similar to Purok A, Purok B also has a long-standing issue with establishing settlements along the riverbanks. Despite several proposed efforts for relocation, the residents still refuse to move elsewhere as they already consider the area their home. According to a respondent, they have experienced several instances of attempting to demolish their homes but their advocacy for being environmental stewards of Davao River remains resolute.

Ikapila na mi nakasinati [ma'am] nga testingan nila og demolish among mga balay kay pahawaon na daw lagi mi. Before [ma'am], nagkagrabe gyud ang ilang pagpamugos; ni-relax lang ron kay nahuman na ang pandemic. Pero maski ingon ana, wala gihapon mi nagpalupig labi na sa among adbokasiya nga mag atiman sa Davao River.

(We've had several encounters where they try to demolish our homes because they want us to leave. Before the pandemic, they were really persistent in wanting us to leave; but now, somehow, they stopped bothering us. Despite the circumstances, we continue to fight for our advocacy in protecting Davao River.)

As for the unfolding of events during the flood, the two youngest respondents experienced firsthand the wrath of Vinta when they were going back and forth in the community rescuing people on a rubber boat. According to them, the presence of the map made their tasks easier because only the roofs of the houses were visible from afar.

Member man gud ko sa evacuation and transport committee. Trabaho gyud nako nga mag assist sa mga residents diri sa among area inig panahon na mamakwit. Kadtong Vinta, nagamit jud namo ang mapa ato kay gikan sa layo [ma'am] ang atop na lang jud intawon ang makita. Gigamit namo ang mapa para ma-identify namo kung kinsa pa ang mga nanginahanglan og rescue.

(I am a member of the evacuation and transport committee. It is my job to assist residents during evacuation. During Vinta, we really utilized the map because you can only see the roofs of the houses from a distance. We used the map to identify the households that needed rescuing.)

A PDAT youth member, on the other hand, recalled how the other residents forgot to secure their pets and livestock in a hurry to escape the rising river. They used the map and identified the households that were not able to take their livestock with them. They rescued three pigs with them which were apparently the lone source of income for the resident.

Kami ato [ma'am] nagsabay mi og pangita sa baboy kay at that time, gisalo na sa barangay ang pagbakwit sa mga tao. Naay residente man gud nga niingon wa daw niya nadala iyang mga baboy unya sweeper na mi ato. Diri sa amo [ma'am] magbuhi og kanding or baboy para ibaligya. Kasagaran sad ani sa ila, mao ra pud ang main source of income ba.

(We were together when we received a report that a resident was not able to bring her pigs to the evacuation center. At that time, the barangay already taken over the evacuation process, so we were assigned as sweepers. Here in our community, people often raise goats and pigs to sell to the market, and for the majority of them, it is their only source of livelihood.)

One of them also reiterated that despite being the youngest member of the team, he feels fulfilled when working with the purok, especially in times of disaster. He is a proud member of the LGBTQIA+ community and ever since, he never felt out of place or belittled when it comes to his skills. According to him, he has always been public with his gender orientation, and he admitted that not everyone is willing to accept him for who he really is. Hence, he was thankful for PDAT who undoubtedly trusted his abilities and even included him in training sessions for evacuation conducted by CDRRMO.

Siguro [ma'am] gusto ra pud nako isingit na very welcoming jud ang PDAT sa akoo. As a part of the LGBT community, wa jud ko naka-experience nga ilaha ko gimaliit diri. Di porket bayot ko, magpuyo na ko sa balay. Ilaha jud ko gisaligan nga murespond sa ground.

(I also want to mention how welcoming the PDAT was when I first signed up. As a part of the LGBT community, I never experienced being belittled by them. They really trusted me to respond on the ground.)

Similar to the situation observed in Purok A, Purok B also used the base maps in a similar manner wherein they were able to locate residents and livestock by referring to the hand-drawn information provided. Another factor that can be investigated is the relatively close-knit communities that are involved in the study. Both puroks know the residents to the point that they gained knowledge into the personal information and main source of livelihood of their fellow community members. Rescuers and PDAT members can easily find their way through the rushing floodwaters because they are familiar with every nook and cranny of the area.

Preferred Guidelines in Determining GIS Information of Purok B

Similar to Purok A, Purok B also has previous knowledge when it comes to GIS-based mapping. As a matter of fact, three out of the five respondents were recruited by CENRO to assist in geotagging the locations of malibago trees way back in 2019. According to the PDRM president, they were taught how to operate the GPS tracking unit used by the deployed CENRO officials.

Gitun-an na namo na sa una kauban ang CENRO kay nag mapa man sad sila diri sa mga natanom na namo nga malibago para daw sa ilahang inventory. Gitudluan mi kung unsaon pag pindot sa tracker ug pag set up sa coordinates aron eksakto pud didto sa mapa.

(We were taught by CENRO how to operate the GPS tracking unit since they came here to tag the locations of our malibago trees for their inventory. They taught us how to set up the satellite connection of the device to produce the exact coordinates that will be used for the map.)

Based on the interviews, Purok B respondents were quite adept in data collection, specifically in creating geopoints, but were admittedly not aware of generating a map through QGIS software. One of the youngest respondents added that the process seems intimidating for him because it would involve high technical knowledge as well as owning computers powerful enough to handle large amounts of data.

Intimidating siya para nako kay technical man gud kaayo tan-awon ang pag generate og mapa. Kinahanglan sad namo og mga laptop nga makakaya sa software [ma'am].

(It is intimidating since generating a map needs technical skills. We also need laptops that can carry the software.)

As for the preferred guidelines in developing GIS maps for the community, a respondent suggested that the most important part that he wants to include is the presence of malibago trees within the area. According to him, planting the malibago trees completely changed their lives since the whole purok could financially benefit from it.

Diri sa amo, importante ang malibago mao na gusto nako na siya ipaapil sa mapa. Ang mga punuan nga naa diri, mao sad na sila ang nakahatag sa amo og panginabuhian pinaagi sa malibago nursery.

(Here in our community, the location of malibago trees is important and I want to include it in the map. The trees that are planted here are also our source of income through the malibago nursery.)

Back in 2018, the PDRM president initiated establishing their own malibago nursery for the community project to be sustainable. Later on, several residents helped in taking care of malibago seedlings to be sold to colleges, government agencies, and volunteer groups who would choose Purok 8 as their tree planting site. Another respondent added that putting the location of the malibago nursery on the map would validate their efforts as a community.

Aside pud anang location sa mga malibago, murag nindot pud apilon ang malibago nursery. Para man gud sa akoo, inig makita nako ang malibago nursery kay makadumdom ko sa among kahago para mahimo siyang successful.

(Aside from the location of the malibago trees, I think that it would also be nice to include the malibago nursery on the map. Everytime I see the malibago nursery, I am always reminded of our efforts that made the venture successful.)

Similar to the inputs of the respondents from Purok A, the community also wanted to immortalize the structures that made their purok unique in its own right. Additionally, a member of the PDAT youth suggested including the location of the school on the map because it is also one of the biggest achievements of the PDAT for the children in the community.

Unta maapil sad ang school sa among mapa. Kani man gud na school ang nag donate og materyales ani kay ang Brokenshire College. Sa sige nila og balik balik diri, nahimo na mi nila nga beneficiary.

(I hope that the school gets included in the map. Brokenshire College donated the materials for the school. They were consistently returning here for their NSTP so they decided that they would have us as beneficiaries.)

The school also served as an important part of the community because the structure is an output of their effort in maintaining the malibago nursery. Additionally, the school is the only daycare center in the barangay which makes education accessible not only to the residents but also to their neighboring puroks.

Interpretation of Flood Hazard Maps

After the initial interview conducted by the researcher prior to the generation of maps, the data collected was then fed into the QGIS software and later presented to the respondents to record their own interpretations. The GIS-based map of Purok B is found below.

Figure 8.
Community base map of Purok B produced using QGIS.

Upon taking a closer look at the map, the immediate observation would be that the number of households in Purok B is greater than that of Purok A. Residents of Purok B also plant more trees in their neighborhood since they have access to malibago seedlings provided by PDRM. As a communication tool, the purok can easily be interpreted as an environment-conscious community because of its initiative in establishing a plant nursery.

According to the PDRM president, he prefers the layout of the digitized maps compared to the base maps because of how concise and compact the information is.

Ganahan jud ko sa dagway sa GIS nga mapa. Aside sa accurate gyud ang location sa mga balay, akong napansin sad kay dasok tanan impormasyon bahin sa komunidad kumpara atong gi-drawing lang nga mapa. Isip usa ka senior citizen, dali ra siya sabton para nako.

(I like how the GIS maps look. Aside from the accurate location of the households, I noticed that the community information is more compact compared to the ones that were only drawn by hand. As a senior citizen myself, I found it easy to understand.)

A PDAT youth member chimed in on the discussion by saying that the data presented using GIS-based maps accurately represent the community by including all the requested features which were discussed earlier by the respondents. The presence of the malibago trees and malibago nursery clearly defined the advocacy of the community. He also added that the layout is easy to understand because of the presence of the legend found on the rightmost portion of the map.

Na-appreciate nako siya [ma'am] kay naapil gyud tong mga feature nga diri ra makita sa among community. Dali ra pud siya sabton kay aduna may legend nga makita nato sa right part sa mapa. Ganahan sad ko nga naay naka indicate kung pila kabuok tao ang nakapuyo ana nga balay kay importante pud na siya sa rescue.

(I appreciated it because the features that are unique in our community were included. It was also easy to understand because of the legend located on the right portion of the map. I like how the household colors indicate the number of people living under one roof because that function is the most important in search and rescue.)

Figure 9.
Flood hazard map of Purok B produced using QGIS.

The generated flood hazard map of the community already tells a story of how a quarter of the houses in the purok were damaged when TS Vinta flooded the city. Aside from the houses being made of salvaged and makeshift materials, they are also set up extremely close to the riverbank where they became subjects of rapid water run-off.

Additionally, the youngest respondent also shared that although the map looks easy to understand, the map features might be appreciated more when looked through the computer. He added that closely studying household information using the software would increase the understanding of how GIS works.

Personally, mas pilion jud nako ang GIS map [ma'am] pero I think mas ma-appreciate sa mga tao kung kahibalo sad mi mugamit sa software mismo. Kay didto man jud makita ang data og tarong.

(Personally, I would choose the GIS map but I think the technology would be more appreciated if people learned how to use the software since the data can be loaded there.)

To further discuss the opinion raised by a PDAT youth member, the data displayed on the map when printed cannot reflect the entirety of the gathered community information. Most of the information can only be accessed through the QGIS software since the data are already embedded in the system. However, the desired information can always be interpreted through a map by configuring the settings through the software.

Participants' Themes

The purpose of this study is to identify the insights of the residents with regard to identifying the GIS-based flood hazard map templates. The research also highlights the lived experiences of the PDAT members through the use of maps in disaster response. Furthermore, this study presents the understanding of local communities about the differences between traditional and GIS-based flood hazard maps.

During the interview, there were several common themes that arose from both puroks about their lived experiences related to their preferred template for their GIS-based maps. The following categories were created to organize the observed commonalities amongst the statements of the respondents: a) Inclusivity; b) Highlighting peculiarities of the community; and c) Validation of their community effort.

Inclusivity

For both puroks, it is imperative that they want to feel included and heard when it comes to decision-making in their communities. As for Purok A, being the only Muslim community prompted them to include distinct structures that can only be found in their area such as the mosque and madrasah. Respondents also reiterated instances where they experienced discrimination not only from their neighboring Christian communities but also from the local government. Incidents that arose during the interview consisted of hate speech and religious profiling.

Parents whom the researcher encountered during the data gathering process expressed that most of their children are being called “muklo” in school which is a pejorative term used against Muslims. The etymology of the word was first used by soldiers to pertain to Moro insurgents. Later, the term was carried over and used as an ethnic slur which is unfortunately still rampant in Mindanao.

The tribal leader of Purok A also shared that people passing by in their community would make snide remarks such as, “Basta mga balay sa Muslim, hugaw” (A Muslim home is always dirty) and “Tarongi imong sinina kay mura ka og Muslim” (Go fix your clothes because you look like a Muslim). The other respondents also agreed that they would hear comments like this and would find it more difficult to integrate into society; hence, they usually just communicate within their own circle.

As for Purok B, the struggle to be recognized as a functioning purok despite the land reclamation issues has been ongoing for the past 23 years. There were numerous attempts to demolish their homes by the city government, yet they remain steadfast in their advocacy of protecting the Davao River. According to the PDRM president, he has lived in the community for almost 25 years so it would be difficult

for him to find another place to call home especially since he feels like he is too old to start over.

Diri na man gyud ko nagkapamilya ug nanigulang. Gusto pud unta nako diri na mamatay. Lisod na para nako ang mubalhin ug mangita og lain balay.

(I started a family here and grew old here. I also would want to spend my final days here. It would be difficult for me to relocate and find a new home.)

For the community, the inclusion of the malibago trees and malibago nursery is a testament to their efforts that despite being labeled as “squatters” by others, they still try to help protect the environment in their own way.

Highlighting Peculiarities of the Community

Communities often have unique cultural practices, traditions, and customs that are essential to their identity. Highlighting the peculiarities can open up conversations about important issues in a community. For both puroks that are featured in the study, there are several differences that were noted since both have a different set of values.

A concern that was discussed during the interview with Purok A was that the younger generation is not as involved when it comes to decision-making in the community. In Purok A, where the majority of the residents belong to the Kalagan tribe, The tribal leader shared that the youth opt to not participate in their meetings and traditions due to varying reasons.

Akong napansin diri sa amo, dili na kaayo gaampo sa mosque ang mga batan-on. Pipila na lang pud ang nagaskwela sa madrasah magtuon og Quran.

(What I noticed in the community is that the younger generations do not frequent the mosque anymore. Only a handful of children also go to the madrasah to learn the Quran.)

Hence, the inclusion of the structures that fully represent their identity as Muslims. The PDAT youth member from Purok A added to the discussion by sharing that creating maps and being involved in disaster management do not sound appealing to people her age anymore as they are more focused on leaving the community in search of better opportunities.

Ang mga batan-on diri sa amoa, dili na sila interesado muapil bahin anang disaster management. Kasagaran man gud sa ilaha ang focus kay makahawa diri ug makatrabaho.

(The younger generation here in our community is not interested in joining discussions regarding disaster management. Most of them are focused on leaving the neighborhood to find a job.)

On the other hand, a different situation can be observed in Purok B where the presence of active youth members is clearly visible. As a matter of fact, the majority of the PDAT responders are composed of members aged 16-25. The barangay is also supportive of their resourcefulness by providing ample training on disaster management to the responders.

The peculiarity highlighted by the respondents during the discussion was the need to establish the presence of malibago trees and malibago nursery within the community. In Davao City, Purok B was lauded as the pioneering community to

adopt the project related to environmental protection and was recognized by CENRO and DENR because of their initiative.

Validation of Community Efforts

During the onslaught of Typhoon Vinta, the mosque and madrasah in Purok A were almost fully immersed in flood with high-water marks still visible near its ceilings. Since then, the residents tried their best to restore the most important structures in their community. According to the purok leader, they looked for sponsors to donate resources for the restoration of their mosque and madrasah since the residents were also short of finances.

Naningkamot mi ato nga makakita mi og sponsor para sa pintura ug uban pa nga materyales. Dili man sad mi maka-solicit diri kay utro pud short og cash.

(We tried our best to find sponsors for the paint and other materials. We cannot solicit funds from the residents because they do not have anything to give.)

After weeks of finding adequate sponsorship, the residents finally collected enough funds to renovate the mosque and madrasah. At the time of the visit for data gathering, the respondents shared that the area is currently experiencing rotational water supply due to the ongoing road widening projects within the vicinity. The issue is more serious than it seems because according to Muslim tradition, they must perform *wudu* which means 'to shower' before entering the mosque and madrasah. As a result, several residents opted to pray in their homes instead of gathering at a communal place like the mosque which greatly reduced the number of attendees.

In Purok B, they have always wanted the maps to validate their efforts in maintaining their malibago tree planting initiative which resulted to more community projects supported by the barangay. One of the projects was the community garden officiated by a respondent in which residents can freely get vegetables for their daily sustenance. The idea started during the height of the pandemic when most of the residents were laid off from work. According to her, she executed the plan out of her own accord because her family was struggling to put food on the table at the height of the pandemic.

Kani nga vegetable garden, nagsugod ni kay ako mismo naglisod pangita og panud-an atong panahona. Siguro kung wala ang kita gikan atong pagpamaligya namo og malibago, wala sad koy ikapundar ani.

(This vegetable garden started when I found it difficult to put food on the table. If it were not for my earnings from the malibago seedlings I sold, I would not be able to fund the project.)

Maps are established as visual tools because they represent spatial information and geographic data. They provide a visual depiction of the Earth's surface, showing the locations of various features, such as cities, rivers, mountains, and roads, in relation to one another. Maps are also considered visual representations of a more efficient and effective way to communicate complex spatial information. People can quickly grasp the layout and relationships between geographic features by looking at a map, as opposed to reading a lengthy description.

However, for the PDAT members of both puroks, maps are not just considered essential tools in navigation and decision-making. The maps also depict

their stories as community members constantly facing the threat of floods brought about by climate change. Additionally, these maps also tell the stories of how they adapt to the changing times by fostering teamwork and innovation.

Following the work of Sonja K. Foss on visual rhetoric, the context of maps can be seen as effective communication tools for several key reasons. Foss emphasizes the power of multimodal communication where visuals, in combination with text or other forms of communication, can enhance the overall message. Maps use a combination of symbols, colors, and spatial relationships making them multimodal tools that convey information more comprehensively than text alone.

Visual rhetoric, according to Foss, has the potential to be more universally understood. Maps are visual representations of spatial information that transcend language barriers and can be interpreted by the general public. In the case of the communities featured in this study, both puroks have different cultural backgrounds and yet they depend on a similar map to make informed decisions.

Additionally, the framework also highlighted the intentional design choices in visual communication. Maps employ various rhetorical strategies in their design such as color choice, use of symbols, scale, and visual hierarchy to guide the viewer's interpretation and understanding—thereby influencing their perception of the information being conveyed. In the context of this research, the respondents specifically requested symbols to represent the structures that are unique to their own purok; thereby also telling a story about the community initiatives they have managed to sustain over the years.

Chapter VI

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SUMMARY

Across the Philippines, issues surrounding watershed management are ecologically, socially, economically, and politically complex. Through the years, subsequent environmental degradation has been increasingly documented, and Davao City is no exception. Along the high-risk riverbanks of the Davao River are the poorest, most vulnerable, and the worst affected by increasing disasters, take residence, and conduct their fragile livelihood.

After further review and consultation with authorities, the communities featured in the study are the two most flood-prone puroks in Davao City. Both communities are located along the river which makes them vulnerable to floods and landslides. In times of disaster, PDAT members heavily rely on their community hand-drawn base maps for rescue and relief operations. However, the hand-drawn base maps are not geographically accurate since they contain a lot of humanistic information mainly deciding on what is physically seen by the human eye. Digitizing the maps would greatly help the community responders in accurately determining the location of households which in turn would provide information for evacuation purposes.

As a matter of fact, the hand-drawn base maps were already used at the height of Tropical Storm Vinta wherein responders used the map to identify the households who need to be prioritized and rescued. According to the accounts of PDAT members, the maps are also being utilized in times of heavy rains wherein the

community determines the households that would most likely be affected in case the river's water levels continue to increase over time.

During the interview, the respondents preferred to feel included in the decision-making process of their communities through the presence of maps. Both puroks wanted to highlight the unique structures present in their area which is consequently a part of their customs and traditions. Each purok has its own set of peculiarities that might be difficult to capture through a mass-scale production of maps similar to the practice of the city government. The respondents also wanted the maps to validate the time and effort they put into making their projects sustainable for the entire community.

When designing and writing GIS information for a general audience, it's crucial to ensure accessibility to people no matter their age or educational background. The respondents wanted elements that are clear, simple, and directly support the text. Hence, the usage of contrasting colors and simple symbols to enhance understanding is essential to maintain the simplicity of the material. In the context of the study, the PDAT respondents wanted plain elements to represent the places that they wanted to be seen on the digitized map. Additionally, cultural diversity and inclusivity were considered in the design and content. Ensuring that the information provided is respectful and relevant to various cultural backgrounds within the target audience is another way for the community to feel seen and understood.

Interpreting flood hazard maps can be challenging for the general public since understanding these maps requires the ability to comprehend spatial representations at varying levels of risk. Describing high, moderate, and low-risk areas, might be difficult without clear visual indicators or accompanying textual explanations. Hence,

different colors were used to distinguish the zones based on the firsthand accounts of the respondents during the last tropical storm that affected the community. The PDAT members also highlighted the changes in the spatial representation of the flood-prone areas in relation to their hand-drawn base maps that are more intuitive rather than scientific.

The data gathered reflects that although the community prefers digitized maps, it also requires being adept in the technology which the community lacks the resources to do so. The minimum requirements to sustain feeding information into a digitized map would be a laptop and a stable internet connection. Hence, the digital divide continues to exist even in the field of disaster risk reduction at the community level.

Even if people have access to digital technologies, there can be a disparity in how they use them. This can be influenced by factors such as digital literacy, technical skills, and the relevance of digital resources. Some individuals or groups may not fully utilize digital tools and the internet due to a lack of knowledge or understanding.

CONCLUSION

The visual rhetoric preferred by the purok members shows that they want to include the distinct features of the community to highlight their peculiarities. For example, Purok 27 which is a predominantly Muslim community composed of an indigenous group called *Kalagan*, specified to include their mosque and madrasah when geotagging locations. On the other hand, Purok 8 wanted to include the designated area for the *malibago* nursery along with the current location of the full-

grown *malibago* trees scattered along the riverbanks. The community wanted to preserve their own identity by including the characteristics that is unique to their area.

A map is not just made up of figures in order to determine spatial information; instead, it also tells a story about the community. Some stories are relatively simple, such as “You are here” or “Here is how to get from Point A to Point B.” Some are more complex, such as the portrayal of the causes and effects of drought, or the relationship between unemployment and income patterns. In this case, the maps depict the story of a community constantly plagued by environmental hazards such as floods and landslides as well as socio-political issues like displacement.

Although the community wanted the digitized version of the maps, they were adamant about sustaining the digitized version given that they lack proper training and equipment to input information to the QGIS software. Therefore, they still gravitate towards hand-drawn two-dimensional base maps due to the easy access to the traditional method of pen and paper. Another factor to consider is that the majority of the community responders consider themselves behind in adopting new technologies, so they also have a challenging time learning digital mapping.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Despite the numerous projects launched by CPDO to assist in digitizing maps, the current method of simply turning over the maps to the community proves to be unsustainable since the scope of the maps focuses on the barangay level. Since

Davao City has 182 barangays, the purok level often gets left behind in terms of appearing on maps.

The creation of effective GIS information hinges on several key guidelines. Firstly, simplicity and clarity are paramount. Maps should utilize plain language devoid of technical jargon ensuring explanations are easily understandable. Clear visual aids such as maps, charts, and diagrams should be incorporated to supplement the written content for easier interpretation of the material. Contextual relevance is also crucial, especially at the community level; providing explanations on the significance of the GIS data in everyday life and making connections that resonate with the intended audience is vital to fully appreciate the purpose of the maps. Finally, feedback collection from the community is essential to refine and optimize the GIS information for maximum comprehension and usability.

However, the Philippines still has a huge digital divide that is yet to be addressed given that over half of the population is considered internet-poor. Urban centers often have better internet infrastructure and connectivity compared to remote or rural areas, where access to high-speed internet remains limited or sometimes non-existent. For decades, the digital divide caused significant inequalities in access to social and economic services, especially in the field of disaster risk reduction. Economic factors also play a substantial role in the digital divide where low-income households often struggle to afford internet services or the necessary devices like computers or smartphones. This exacerbates the gap between those who can afford access to technology and those who cannot.

For the purpose of future studies, the researcher must propose alternative ways to maximize the digital maps and preserve them for future generations to

come. A strategy that can be explored is to conduct comprehensive training for the localization of GIS technology in low-income and high-risk areas. Additionally, the involvement of youth community members in the localization of digital maps is a great avenue for the advocacy to be more inclusive and sustainable in the long run.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

April 11, 2023

HON. PACITO D. CAÑETE, JR.
Punong Barangay
Barangay Ma-a, Davao City

**SUBJECT: REQUEST FOR AN INTERVIEW WITH PUROK DISASTER ACTION TEAM (PDAT)
VOLUNTEERS FOR A MASTER'S THESIS**

Dear Hon. Cañete:

Greetings!

I am a second-year graduating student at University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) taking up MA Development Communication. I am currently writing my master's thesis with the working title, "Identifying Ideal Templates Through Visual Rhetoric for GIS-based Flood Hazard Maps in Disaster-prone Communities within Davao City."

This research aims to determine the impact of visual communication in GIS-based flood hazard maps of select urban areas in Davao City. Since I have worked for Mindanao Land Foundation from 2017-2020, I specifically chose Barangay Ma-a to be a part of my sample size. The organization has worked with PDAT volunteers during its project implementation and has provided them with knowledge on capability building and liaising with government agencies such as City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office.

In connection with this, I cannot proceed with my thesis without sufficient input from the PDAT volunteers themselves. Hence, I would like to ask for your permission to conduct a focus group discussion with the volunteers to get the necessary information needed to complete the research. Any relevant information and assistance coming from the barangay would also be greatly appreciated.

If you have any questions or concerns regarding my request, please feel free to contact me at 09192333880. I am looking forward to hearing your positive response. Thank you and more power.

Respectfully,

FAYE JANICA V. CABIZA

APPENDIX B

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES OPEN UNIVERSITY

April 11, 2023

HON. MARK ANTHONY C. CAYETANO
Punong Barangay
Barangay 10-A, Davao City

**SUBJECT: REQUEST FOR AN INTERVIEW WITH PUROK DISASTER ACTION TEAM (PDAT)
VOLUNTEERS FOR A MASTER'S THESIS**

Dear Hon. Cayetano:

Greetings!

I am a second-year graduating student at University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) taking up MA Development Communication. I am currently writing my master's thesis with the working title, "Identifying Ideal Templates Through Visual Rhetoric for GIS-based Flood Hazard Maps in Disaster-prone Communities within Davao City."

This research aims to determine the impact of visual communication in GIS-based flood hazard maps of select urban areas in Davao City. Since I have worked for Mindanao Land Foundation from 2017-2020, I specifically chose Barangay 10-A to be a part of my sample size. The organization has worked with PDAT volunteers during its project implementation and has provided them with knowledge on capability building and liaising with government agencies such as City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office.

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If you have any questions or concerns regarding my request, please feel free to contact me at 09192333880. I am looking forward to hearing your positive response. Thank you and more power.

Respectfully,

FAYE JANICA V. CABIZA